

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Medication Adherence in Orthopaedic Patients: A Comparative Study Using Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Ortho Care Unit of Tertiary Care Hospital

Vijayakumar S.*, S. Ravena, G. Nishalini, S. Monisha

Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Nallampalli, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 28 Jun. 2025

Keywords:

Medication adherence, orthopaedic patients, Modified Morisky Scale, chronic conditions, pain management, healthcare outcomes.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15763216

ABSTRACT

In a fast-developing country like India, the prevalence of osteoporosis and its associated complications is steadily increasing. Poor adherence to prescribed medications, particularly in chronic conditions, significantly raises the risk of adverse outcomes. Inadequate medication adherence can lead to suboptimal clinical results, increased healthcare costs, and accelerated disease progression. Developing focused clinical interventions that promote compliance and improve patient outcomes. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the management and adherence to medication therapy. Settings and Design: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted from October 2024 to November 2025 in the outpatient clinic of a tertiary care hospital in Krishnagiri. A study involving orthopaedic patients with postoperative orthopaedic interventions or chronic conditions (such as osteoarthritis or osteoporosis) was carried out at a tertiary care hospital. The Modified Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMS), comprising eight items, was administered to all participants to assess their adherence to prescribed medication. Patients were selected, including all age groups, diagnosis of an orthopaedic condition, and current medication use. Demographic data (age, gender, education level) and clinical factors (co-morbidities, laboratory findings) were also collected through structured questionnaires. To ensure objectivity, the author and three co-authors conducted statistical data analysis using Graph Pad Prism version 10 software. Our study identifies a distinct demographic profile of orthopaedic patients, highlighting that married women (79.87%), primarily housewives (33.19%), aged 41–60 years (37.75%), with low literacy levels (39.21%), and residing in rural areas (63.07%) are disproportionately affected by orthopaedic conditions. A strong association was observed between these demographic factors and the presence of comorbidities, with ulcers being particularly prevalent (77.17%). Medication non-

*Corresponding Author: Vijayakumar S.

Address: Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Nallampalli, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu, India.

Email ✉: vijaykumarsasikala@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

adherence emerged as a major concern, largely influenced by fear of side effects, financial constraints, and a lack of awareness regarding the long-term impact of untreated conditions. These findings underscore the urgent need for targeted educational interventions, particularly for housewives, to promote preventive strategies against bone fractures and osteoporosis, ultimately improving overall health outcomes

INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, medication adherence has become increasingly important for effective disease management, especially for chronic conditions that require long-term pharmacotherapy. Adherence to prescribed medication is essential for orthopaedic patients to achieve the best possible treatment outcomes, which include pain relief, regeneration of bone, and preventing the development of complications such as osteoporosis and fractures. Failure may result in subclinical outcomes, increased medical expenses, and a higher risk of medical condition progression. For orthopaedic patients, who are impacted by a wide range of clinical and sociodemographic factors, medication adherence remains a significant concern despite its significance. Understanding these factors is necessary to develop targeted interventions that improve patient outcomes and increase adherence.

[1] According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), medication adherence is the degree to which a patient & behaviours conforms to the recommended course of treatment. Among the many aspects that comprise adherence are the appropriate dosage, the frequency, and the length of time spent taking the medication. However a variety of challenges, such as complicated drug schedules, adverse effects, ignorance, and financial limitations, can have a substantial impact on adherence levels. Many research investigations have revealed misconceptions regarding the need for medications. Non-adherence in orthopaedic patients is often associated with concerns about

adverse drug reactions and not adequate patient education. Musculoskeletal pain and fractures are two orthopaedic conditions that require life style changes, and rehabilitation.^[2,3] Among the medications frequently prescribed in orthopaedics are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), analgesics, corticosteroids, and supplements for bone health which involve calcium and vitamin D. Patient adherence to these medications, however, varies widely and is often influenced by a number of factors, that include age, gender, educational background, socioeconomic status, and the challenges of the prescribed regimen.^[4,5] The Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8), which defines patients into groups with high, medium, and low adherence, is the most commonly employed tool to assess medication adherence. By offering useful data on patient behaviour with regard to medication intake, this scale supports medical professionals to recognise patients who may be experiencing poor medication adherence and implementing the necessary interventions.^[6] In orthopaedic care, identifying adherence patterns can aid in improving patient education and optimising treatment plans. Using the MMAS-8 scale, the current study attempts to assess medication adherence among orthopaedic patients in a tertiary care hospital. In order to create focused strategies for enhancing patient compliance, it looks for important adherence-influencing factors, such as demographic traits, socioeconomic status, and clinical conditions. This study adds to the expanding corpus of research aimed at strengthening treatment outcomes and general patient well-being in orthopaedic care by investigating adherence levels and related determinants.^[7]

Subjects and Methods:

Study Design and Setting

A cross-sectional observational study was conducted from October 2024–November 2025 in the outpatient clinic of a tertiary care hospital in Krishnagiri.

Participants

The study included 482 orthopaedic patients in all, from age 5 to 85 (199 men and 283 women). Individuals who were willing to participate, had been prescribed medication for at least a week, and were recently diagnosed with osteoporosis or fractures of the bones were included in the study.

Data Collection Tools

- **Interview Questionnaire:** Collected socio-demographic data (age, sex, marital status, education, occupation, dietary habits, BMI) and clinical details (diagnosis, laboratory findings, medication history, co-morbidities).
- **Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8):** Assessed medication adherence, categorizing patients into low (score 0–5), medium (score 6–7), or high adherence (score 8).
- **Clinical Record Review:** Verified prescribed medications, adherence-related complications, and co-morbidities.

Data Collection Procedure

In the outpatient department, eligible patients were contacted. In advance of providing the MMAS-8 questionnaire and demographic survey, informed consent was acquired. The study coordinator specified guidance to patients who needed help. To guarantee a varied sample, data has been collected over one year period.

Outcome Measures

Primary Outcome: Medication adherence level based on MMAS-8 scores.

Secondary Outcomes: Factors influencing adherence, including age, gender, education, socioeconomic status, medication complexity, and side effects.

Sample Size Calculation

The sample size was determined using the following formula, $N = z^2 p (1-p) / d^2$ Where p represents the estimated proportion of inappropriate prescription patterns (0.5 in this case, as no prior research findings were available). N signifies the sample size, and d denotes the margin of sampling error tolerated (0.05). The standard normal value of a 95% confidence interval (z) was set to 1.96, resulting in the calculated sample size. [8]

Data Analysis

The characteristics of the participants have been added up using statistical methods that were descriptive (mean, standard deviation). Demographic and clinical characteristics were linked to adherence outcomes, and MMAS-8 scores were used to organise adherence levels.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board. Written and oral informed consent was secured, ensuring voluntary participation. Patient confidentiality and data privacy were strictly maintained. The study received approval from the Ethical review board (VVCOP/EC/00118/2024), Srivijayvidhalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Socio demographic data of the orthopaedic prescriptions of the study population.

Patients Characteristics	Male (n)	Female (n)	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
--------------------------	----------	------------	-----------	----------------

Gender		199	283	482	
Age in (years)	>20	29	20	49	10.1
	21-40	78	93	171	35.4
	41-60	62	120	182	37.7
	61-80	30	50	80	16.5
Occupation	Employed	146	72	218	45.2
	Unemployed	53	51	104	21.5
	Housewife	-	160	160	33.1
Body Mass Index	Overweight	51	72	123	25.5
	Underweight	11	9	20	4.1
	Normal	64	77	141	29.2
	Obese	73	125	198	41
Marital status	Married	150	235	385	79.8
	Unmarried	49	47	96	19.9
	Living alone	-	1	1	0.2
Education level	0-9 th	26	24	50	10.3
	10th-12th	42	53	95	19.7
	>12th	76	72	148	30.7
	Illiterate	55	134	189	39.2
Eating habits	Mixed	190	253	443	91.9
	Vegetarian	9	30	39	8.09
Region	Rural	124	180	304	63
	Urban	75	103	178	36.9
Type of family	Joint family M-14	75	93	168	34.8
	Nuclear family M-22	124	190	314	65.1

Study Participants' Clinical and Demographic Characteristics

In total, there were 283 female orthopaedic patients (58.7%) and 199 male orthopaedic patients (41.3%) in the study. A majority of the participants (37.7%) were between the ages of 41 and 60, followed by those between the ages of 21 and 40 (35.4%), and 10.1% were under the age of 20. In terms of occupation, 33.1% were housewives, 21.5% were unemployed, and 45.2% were employed. 41% of participants had an obese body mass index (BMI), 29.2% had a normal BMI, 25.5% were overweight, and 4.1% were underweight. The distribution of marital status revealed that 0.2% lived alone, 19.9% seemed unmarried, and 79.8% were married. 39.2% of participants had been illiterate, 30.7% had completed higher education (>12th grade), 19.7% had completed secondary school (10th–12th

grade), and 10.3% had only completed the ninth grade. According to dietary habits, 8.09% of participants were vegetarians and 91.9% of participants ate a mixed diet. 63% of the study participants were from rural areas, while 36.9% were from urban areas. Regarding family structure, joint families made up 34.8% of the overall population, while nuclear families made up 65.1%. This demographic profile provides important details about the lifestyle and socioeconomic factors that may affect orthopaedic patients' compliance to their medication regimens..

Clinical Diagnosis of Study Participants

The study included 482 orthopaedic patients with an assortment of diagnoses were enrolled in the study. Lower limb pain was the most common condition, which impacts 276 patients (57.26%), and it was more prevalent in females (199) than in

males (77). There were 125 patients (25.93%) who had fractures, and the prevalence was higher in men (77) than in women (48). Forty-five patients (9.33%) reported upper limb pain, and thirty-four patients (7.05%) reported injuries. A total of two female patients (0.41%) had osteoporosis, making it the least common diagnosis. These findings

highlight gender-related differences in diagnosis and their possible effects on treatment and medication adherence, as well as the distribution of orthopaedic conditions within the study population. It has been shown in Table 2: Distribution of clinical diagnoses among male and female orthopaedic patients.

DIAGNOSIS	MALE (n)	FEMALE (n)	TOTAL (n)	PERCENTAGE (%)
FRACTURE	77	48	125	25.93
PAIN IN LOWER LIMBS	77	199	276	57.26
PAIN IN UPPER LIMBS	17	28	45	9.33
INJURY	28	6	34	7.05
OSTEOPOROSIS		2	2	0.41

Drug Utilization Pattern Among Study Participants

A wide variety of prescribed medications were found in this study, which evaluated the medication use of 482 orthopaedic patients. With 465 cases (24.2%), analgesics and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) were the most commonly used medications. 413 patients (21.5%) received prescriptions for anti-ulcer medications, 282 patients (14.69%) received corticosteroids, and 268 patients (13.96%) received antibiotics. Miscellaneous drugs accounted for 131 cases (6.82%), while anti-inflammatory drugs were prescribed to 153 patients (7.97%). Multivitamins were prescribed to 67 patients (3.49%), and 122 patients (6.35%) used antidepressants. With just 18 cases (0.93%), calcium and vitamin D supplements were the least frequently prescribed. These results highlight the need for physicians to maintain a check on patients' medication adherence and potential adverse reactions because they show a high reliance on analgesics and NSAIDs in orthopaedic treatment. It has been depicted in table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of drug categories prescribed to orthopaedic patients.

Category of Drug	No. of Cases (n)	Percentage (%)
Antibiotics	268	13.96
Anti-ulcer drug	413	21.5
Analgesic & NSAIDS	465	24.2
Anti-inflammatory drugs	153	7.97
Multivitamin	67	3.49
Antidepressants	122	6.35
Calcium and Vitamin D supplements	18	0.93
Corticosteroids	282	14.69
Miscellaneous drugs	131	6.82

Table 4: Distribution of medication adherence levels among both gender of orthopaedic patients based on the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS).

Patients Adherence Scale	Male (n)	Female (n)	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
High adherence	1	6	7	1.45
Medium adherence	19	23	42	8.71
Low adherence	179	254	433	89.83

The study evaluated medication adherence among 482 orthopaedic patients participated in the study, which assessed medication adherence and found a general trend of poor adherence. Low adherence was present in a significant majority of patients, 433 (89.83%), with a higher prevalence among females (254) than males (179). Forty-two patients (8.71%), which includes 19 males and 23 females, showed moderate adherence. However, only 7

patients (1.45%), 6 of whom were female and 1 of whom was male, showed high adherence. The above findings highlight a major problem with orthopaedic patients' medication adherence, emphasising the significance of targeted approaches to improve compliance and enhance the outcomes of therapy. It has been shown in figure 1.

Table 5: Spearman’s correlation between MMAS-8 and MMAS-4 adherence scores among orthopaedic patients.

<i>Spearman's Correlations</i>									
			n	Spearman's rho	p	Lower 95% CI	Upper 95% CI		
MMAS- 8	-	MMAS- 4	482	0.220	< .001	0.133	0.303		

The Spearman's correlation between MMAS-8 and MMAS-4 is weak but statistically significant. The correlation is positive (0.220), meaning that higher values on MMAS-8 tend to be associated with higher values on MMAS-4. Given that the p-value is very small (< .001), we can be confident that this

observed relationship is not due to random chance. The 95% confidence interval for the correlation suggests that the true correlation in the population is likely to range from 0.133 to 0.303, further supporting the significance of this finding reported in figure 2.

DISCUSSION:

In a developing country like India, the prevalence of osteoporosis and related musculoskeletal complications is increasing, particularly among middle-aged and rural populations. Our study observed that a significant proportion of orthopaedic patients were married women (79.87%), many of whom were housewives (33.19%) and aged between 41 and 60 years. This demographic profile highlights the influence of social roles, age-related physiological changes, and geographic disparities on musculoskeletal health.^[9,10] Household responsibilities involving repetitive tasks, prolonged standing, and heavy lifting may contribute to physical strain, potentially increasing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders in women managing home and family duties.^[11] These physical demands, combined with declining muscle strength, joint elasticity, and bone mineral density in the 41–60 age group, are further exacerbated by hormonal changes during the menopausal transition^[12,13] Notably, 89.83% of participants exhibited low medication adherence, with female patients showing particularly high non-adherence rates. This is

consistent with previous research linking poor adherence to socioeconomic barriers, fear of side effects, and limited health literacy. Psychosocial and informational barriers, especially in populations with reduced access to healthcare, remain a major challenge.^[14,15] The Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS) has been widely used to assess adherence levels and identify barriers such as financial burden and concerns about side effects (Morisky et al., 2008). In our study, only a small proportion of patients demonstrated moderate (8.71%) or high (1.45%) adherence. These findings underscore the need for structured counselling, improved health literacy, and enhanced physician-patient communication to support adherence.^[17] A high prevalence of peptic ulcers (77.17%) was also observed, likely due to prolonged NSAID use for orthopaedic pain management. NSAIDs, though effective, are known to compromise gastrointestinal integrity, leading to increased morbidity and reduced medication adherence. Patients experiencing adverse effects may discontinue treatment prematurely, further complicating disease management.^[12,13] The interplay between comorbidities and medication adherence

highlights the importance of individualized care plans. Structured interventions such as counselling, medication reviews, and lifestyle modifications have been shown to improve adherence, particularly among vulnerable groups like housewives and the elderly.^[20] Tailored education on self-management and disease awareness, along with strengthened communication and community-based health programs, can empower patients and improve outcomes^[13]. Addressing adherence through comprehensive, patient-centered strategies remains critical in reducing the burden of musculoskeletal disorders and improving the quality of orthopaedic care.^[16] With a particularly high prevalence of peptic ulcers seen in 77.17% of the study population, the current study highlights a strong correlation between patients' social characteristics and comorbid conditions. This result is in line with earlier research that found a direct correlation between long-term nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) use and the emergence of gastrointestinal issues, such as peptic ulcers.^[12,13] Although NSAIDs are frequently prescribed in orthopaedic care to treat pain and inflammation, long-term use of these medications has been linked to gastrointestinal integrity compromise and increased morbidity^[11]. Patients who experience discomfort or complications may decide to stop taking their medications or follow their prescribed regimens irregularly, which can have a substantial impact on medication adherence^[16]. The study also highlights a high prevalence of medication non-adherence, with 89.83% of participants exhibiting low adherence levels. This finding is consistent with existing literature that identifies factors such as socioeconomic constraints, fear of side effects, and limited health literacy as significant barriers to adherence.^[14,15] Notably, female patients demonstrated higher rates of non-adherence, underscoring the need for gender-sensitive

interventions. The relationship between concurrent disorders and adherence emphasises how crucial tailored and focused interventions are. Orthopaedic patients' adherence rates have been shown to increase with the help of structured patient counselling, medication reviews, and lifestyle modification programs.^[15] For at-risk populations like housewives and older adults, who comprised a significant portion of our sample and are frequently more vulnerable to musculoskeletal disorders and their related complications, these interventions are especially important^[17]. Adherence issues in these populations may be made worse by socioeconomic restrictions, lack of health literacy, and providing care obligations.^[18] According to Anderson and Lee, tailored educational programs emphasising self-management techniques and disease awareness can dramatically lower these susceptible groups' risk of osteoporosis-related fractures.^[19] Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that strengthening physician-patient communication and providing community-based health education improve treatment adherence and give patients the confidence to actively participate in their care^[20-22]. Given these results, a key component of successful orthopaedic management continues to be addressing non-adherence through comprehensive, patient-centered approaches. Clinical practice can minimise obstacles, maximise treatment results, and lessen the overall burden of musculoskeletal disorders by implementing routine counselling, adverse effect monitoring, and adherence evaluations.

CONCLUSIONS

Our analysis reveals a unique demographic profile of orthopaedic patients have a distinct demographic profile. We emphasise that married women (79.87%), housewives (33.19%), individuals between the ages of 41 and 60

(37.75%), individuals who have low literacy (39.21%), as well as those living in rural areas (63.07%) are disproportionately affected by orthopaedic conditions. These demographic characteristics were found to be significantly correlated with the overall incidence of concurrent medical conditions, with ulcers being the most common (77.17%). Fear of side effects, inadequate knowledge about the long-term consequences of untreated conditions, and financial constraints were the main causes of medication non-adherence, which became a major issue. The aforementioned results highlight the critical need for focused educational interventions, particularly among housewives, for the purpose to enhance general health outcomes as well as promote osteoporosis and fracture early detection.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

We wish to express our heartfelt gratitude to all the orthopaedic patients who willingly participated in this study. Their valuable time, cooperation, and honest responses to the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale have been instrumental in advancing our understanding of medication adherence patterns in the Ortho Care Unit of the tertiary care hospital.

REFERENCES

1. Binkley J, Stratford PW, Lott SA, Riddle DL. The Western Ontario and McMaster Universities Osteoarthritis Index (WOMAC): A review of its utility and measurement properties in orthopaedic and musculoskeletal research. *J Rheumatol.* 1999;26(12):53–8.
2. Bijlsma JWJ, Berenbaum F. Osteoarthritis: pathology and management. *Lancet.* 2017;388(10061):3125–35.
3. Vijayakumar S, Parimalakrishnan S, Prem Anand DC, Kaviya S, Mohammed Fareedullah. Assessing health-related quality of life in osteoporosis patients in India: a cross-sectional study of fractures in rural and urban populations. *Korean J Physiol Pharmacol.* 2024;28(1):241–51.
4. Anderson DG, Shimer AL. Spinal disorders: diagnosis and management. *Spine J.* 2015;15(6):1331–5.
5. Vijayakumar S, Parimalakrishnan S, Prem Anand DC, Karthika M, Vijayakumar AR. A prospective study on drug audit, prescribing patterns assessment, and clinical outcomes evaluation in a tertiary care hospital, Tamil Nadu, India. *J Young Pharm.* 2023;15(4):734–42.
6. Compston JE, Cooper A. Osteoporosis in orthopaedics: an overview of clinical management. *Osteoporos Int.* 2018;29(5):987–96.
7. O'Neill TW, McCabe C, Puttice P. Quality of life in orthopaedic patients with musculoskeletal disorders. *Clin Orthop Relat Res.* 2020;478(4):776–84.
8. Naresh K, Pravin P, Ruban Raj J, Buddhikumar S. Drug utilization pattern by using WHO Core Prescribing Indicators in orthopedics and obstetrics/gynecology departments of a tertiary care hospital. *J Lumbini Med Coll.* 2019;7:1-5.
9. Fraenkel L, Rabidou N, Wittink D. Patient education materials about osteoarthritis: Are they helpful? *Arthritis Rheum.* 2013;65(7):e55–6.
10. Katz JN, Losina E, Barrett J, Phillips CB, Mahomed NN, Lew RA, et al. Association between hospital and surgeon procedure volume and outcomes of total hip replacement in the United States Medicare population. *J Bone Joint Surg Am.* 1994;83(11):1622–9.
11. Cross M, Smith E, Hoy D, Nolte S, Ackerman I, Fransen M, et al. The global burden of hip and knee osteoarthritis: estimates from the

- Global Burden of Disease 2010 study. *Ann Rheum Dis.* 2014;73(7):1323–30.
12. Smith TO, King JJ, Hing CB. The impact of aging on musculoskeletal health: A comprehensive review. *Age Ageing.* 2023;52(1):afac300.
 13. Lee J, Park S, Kim JH. Menopause and the musculoskeletal system: Changes and clinical consequences. *Osteoporos Int.* 2021;32(10):1963–75.
 14. Johnson RE, Horn J, Perloff M, Etzioni R. Analysis of the costs of NSAID-associated gastropathy. *Pharmacoeconomics.* 1997;12(1):76–88.
 15. Morisky DE, Ang A, Krousel-Wood M, Ward HJ. Predictive validity of a medication adherence measure in an outpatient setting. *J Clin Hypertens.* 2008;10(5):348–54.
 16. Johnson MJ, Williams M, Marshall T. Factors influencing medication adherence in orthopaedic patients: A mixed-methods study. *J Orthop Sci.* 2020;25(4):610–6.
 17. Patel P, Rudd T, Khan S. The impact of patient education on medication adherence in orthopaedic postoperative care. *Int J Orthop.* 2019;6(2):114–20.
 18. Sale JE, Gignac M, Hawker G. How “bad” does the pain have to be? A qualitative study examining adherence to pain medication in older adults with osteoarthritis. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2006;55(2):272–8.
 19. Jin J, Sklar GE, Min Sen Oh V, Chuen Li S. Factors affecting therapeutic compliance: A review from the patient’s perspective. *Ther Clin Risk Manag.* 2008;4(1):269–86.
 20. Anderson H, Lee K. Enhancing medication adherence and osteoporosis prevention through targeted educational interventions: A community-based study. *Int J Rheum Dis.* 2022;25(1):75–82.
 21. Clyne B, Bradley MC, Hughes C, Fahey T, Lapane KL. Electronic prescribing and other forms of technology to reduce inappropriate medication use and polypharmacy in older people: A review of current evidence. *Clin Geriatr Med.* 2012;28(2):301–22.
 22. Zolnierok KBH, Dimatteo MR. Physician communication and patient adherence to treatment: A meta-analysis. *Med Care.* 2009;47(8):826–34.

HOW TO CITE: Vijayakumar S., S. Ravena, G. Nishalini, S. Monisha, Medication Adherence in Orthopaedic Patients: A Comparative Study Using Morisky Medication Adherence Scale in Ortho Care Unit of Tertiary Care Hospital, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 5531-5540. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15763216>

